

Characterizing NCPA for NirvanaVIS

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ABSTRACT

NirvanaVIS is a new instrument for the Large Binocular Telescope that has recently been endorsed by LBTO as part of their 2025 call for new instruments. It is a fast track instrument that takes advantage of the existing LINC-NIRVANA Ground Layer Adaptive Optics (GLAO) system. The instrument will perform speckle imaging in the visible, which benefits from the more stable Point Spread Function (PSF) provided by the AO system. Although the GLAO hardware is proven on-sky, some recalibration will be required for use in NirvanaVIS. Most notably, the non-common path aberrations, which can significantly deteriorate performance if not adequately addressed. This applies regardless of the usage of PSF deconvolution methods (e.g. speckle holography) that are envisioned for NirvanaVIS, as these techniques still benefit from a more compact PSF. With an additional corrector, the Xinetics DM349 belonging to the unused high layer AO system, in NirvanaVIS' optical path, there is a possibility to have a dedicated corrector for quasi-static aberrations alongside the adaptive secondary mirror. This could prove particularly beneficial to an imager like NirvanaVIS, as the additional corrector could help to minimize the non-common path aberrations across the instrument's large field of view. In order to take full advantage, careful consideration of the characterization procedure and correction strategy for these aberrations is required. Here we consider the use of focal plane sharpening and phase diversity methods for NCPA characterization in the context of the NirvanaVIS instrument.

Keywords: NirvanaVIS, NCPA, AO, calibration

1. INTRODUCTION

The NirvanaVIS instrument will perform AO-assisted speckle imaging in the visible. It will have a fast-track to on-sky observations by taking advantage of the existing GLAO system designed for the LINC-NIRVANA (LN) instrument [9, 10, 11, 18]. Using speckle deconvolution techniques, it will achieve (near) diffraction limited

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Figure 1. Simplified overview of NirvanaVIS Optical Path, on the SX side of the LN instrument. The high layer WFS and NIR science camera are drawn in grey to indicate that these parts of the LN bench are not used in NirvanaVIS. GWS indicates the ground layer WFS and CU the calibration unit.

images on the Large Binocular Telescope’s (LBT) 8.2m single-eye aperture [2, 4, 5]. The combination of adaptive optics with speckle imaging on an 8-meter class telescope is novel, with simulations showing the benefits of this combination [6].

This is a significant deviation from the purpose for which the existing hardware was designed, which requires the review of operating procedures of some of the existing hardware. The most significant piece of LN infrastructure used is the GLAO system [17]. Given the changes to the optical path, the use of a different wavelength, and changes to the telescope’s AO infrastructure*, the calibration of the GLAO system has to be revisited.

This paper discusses the characterization of the non-common path aberrations (NCPA).

Correcting for NCPA has become a standard part of the commissioning procedure of AO systems. There are two methods that are frequently used: *Phase Diversity* [7] and *Focal Plane Sharpening* [1]. In the focal plane sharpening method, a live optimization is run. Different shapes are applied to the DM and the effect on the PSF in the science focal plane is recorded. The phase diversity method, on the other hand, uses frames taken intra- and extra-focal from the science plane. A simulated optimization is run, with the wavefront producing the closest PSF to the one recorded is taken to be the NCPA. Both of these methods have shown great results in the past [8, 12, 13, 19], here we consider their use considering the constraints imposed by the architecture of the LN instrument as well as the suitability to the NirvanaVIS use case.

2. THE CASE OF NIRVANAVIS

During the commissioning of LN, a correction for NCPA was measured and used [16], but adapting the methods used to NirvanaVIS is not trivial. At that time, the NCPAs were measured between the high layer Wavefront Sensor (WFS) and the infrared science camera. As the high layer AO system is not used when operating the NirvanaVIS instrument, this procedure has to be reworked, in order to be referenced to the GLAO system. This is more challenging because its WFS uses an annular mirror pick-off, instead of a dichroic, which means the WFS and science camera cannot be illuminated with the same source at the same time.

Sources originally intended for this process are located in the calibration unit, which is downstream from the ground layer WFS (see figure 1). Alternatively, there is a diffraction-limited source available in the telescope’s primary focus (positioned below the adaptive secondary mirror). The use of this source is more constrained however, as its use requires dedicated telescope technical time. The use of the internal calibration sources is therefore only useful for measuring internal variations in the NCPA, but given LN’s modest scientific field-of-view, only the on-axis source was intended for such a task. Off-axis sources were envisioned to be used for the calibration of the high layer WFS and were therefore chosen to be multi-mode fibers, with such a choice motivated by their

*associated with the SOUL AO system upgrade [14, 15]

higher throughput and more forgiving acquisition with the pyramid WFS. All but the on-axis source will produce an extended source in the science focal plane, while their use for NCPA calibration is not well understood in the literature and requires further investigation. Alternatively, there is a possibility to move these sources around the Field of View (FoV) with motorized stages. This would allow the central diffraction limited source to be used at different points in the field sequentially, losing the option to record the NCPA across different points in parallel. This same issue applies to the source in the primary focus as well.

From previous experience with the use of the ground layer WFS system, it is known that movement of the guide star selector motors introduces small but significant aberrations. With the (uncorrected) curved focal plane of LBT, a lateral movement of the guide star selector introduces an additional defocus factor. Also, the rotation of the GWS derotator bearing has been shown to introduce an astigmatism term. During the characterization of the NCPA these factors will have to be measured as well, in order to be able to correct them.

Additional challenges arise when considering the correction for NCPA. With the only corrector conjugated with the ground layer (the adaptive secondary mirror) placed before the GWS, its use for NCPA will degrade the focus on these pyramid WFS, which are known to have degraded performance under such conditions [3]. Alternatively, there is another DM available downstream of the GWS. However, this corrector is conjugated to a layer at an altitude of 7.1 km. This means that, when correcting for aberrations closer to the ground layer, the residual will vary across the FoV, making it impossible to fully correct the NCPA found, and requiring a tradeoff analysis to find the optimal shape to apply.

3. SIMULATIONS

In order to understand the consequences of the use of multi-mode fibers for NCPA characterization, a simple simulation was run. The PSF of such a source was taken to be the convolution of a Gaussian with a FWHM corresponding to the fiber's 0.33" size (when projected on-sky), with the Airy pattern corresponding to the LBT's 8.2m aperture. For the sake of comparison, a perfect single-mode fiber, which consists of only the Airy pattern, is considered as well.

These PSFs are then compared with one aberrated by a single Zernike mode, which tells us the magnitude of their response to NCPA. This is repeated with aberrations of increasing strength to probe the response in the focal plane to each of these modes. Afterwards, this process is performed with one wave of defocus applied (in either direction) as well, to emulate the images taken during a characterization of NCPA using phase diversity. [Figures 2](#) to [4](#) show the results of this. They display the contrast required to sense an aberration of a particular amplitude in the focal plane, which is a measure of their effect compared to the total flux found in an unaberrated frame. In order to quantify the contrast better, some horizontal lines are included that show the limit of the instrument through its expected noise floor (in the shot noise dominated regime). There it becomes clear that the use of multi-mode fibers incurs a significant penalty on the sensitivity to certain modes. Modes such as tip/tilt and coma can still be characterised very well, while some others like trefoil and quadrafoil drop multiple decades requiring many frames in order to detect any amplitude. Interestingly, the application of a static defocus reduces the change to the single-mode PSF more than for the multi-mode PSF, bringing the performance closer together. This is shown in [figures 3](#) and [4](#).

Additional difficulties arise from degeneracy between the modes, as seen by a resolved PSF. [Figure 5](#) shows the response of the PSF to the first 16 Zernike modes (only one of each symmetric pair is shown), through a difference image (an aberrated image with the unaberrated PSF subtracted). Where the PSF of the single-mode fiber shows a distinct response for each mode, many of the multi-mode fiber images are very similar. The extended nature of its PSF washes out a lot of the structure, creating a coma-like response for many modes. A notable exception to this is trefoil, which has its structure preserved. However, this does not hold for quadrafoil, creating a response that resembles trefoil, creating another degeneracy in the response.

4. PROCEDURE

Here the baseline NCPA characterization and correction procedure is outlined. It will be divided into two parts: the variation of the ground layer WFS offsets, and the science arm NCPA. The static GLAO offsets are included in the latter as they cannot be distinguished from NCPA in the science arm of the optical path. The GLAO offsets have to be measured using the source in the primary focus, as it is the only source capable of illuminating the WFS. The variable part of its offsets can be measured by the WFS itself, by measuring differences in the time-averaged slopes with movements of the motorized stages. As these offsets can negatively affect the spot projected on the pyramid when using multiple NGSs, these measured offsets can be applied to the adaptive secondary mirror.

For the science arm NCPA, the Xinetics DM will be used instead. Due to the disparity in conjugation altitude

Figure 2. Comparison of the response to Zernike mode aberrations in the PSF of single- and multi-mode fibers. On the y-axis the required contrast to detect the difference in the PSF induced by a particular Zernike mode (indicated by the color of the marker). A number of horizontal lines show the expected contrast achieved by NirvanaVIS using a sequence of frames, derived from the expected SNR on frames where 75% of the dynamic range is used. Here only the corresponding Zernike mode is applied, without any defocus.

Figure 3. Same as figure 2, but with a defocus of 1 wave applied. This gives a better idea of the performance through the phase diversity method.

Figure 4. Same as figure 2, but with a defocus of -1 wave applied. This gives a better idea of the performance through the phase diversity method.

between these aberrations and their corrector, the use of the phase diversity method becomes significantly more complicated. For the focal plane sharpening method, the effect of this disparity is shown directly. Making the tradeoff between samples across the field of view far simpler. Therefore, this method will serve as the baseline for NirvanaVIS' NCPA characterization strategy.

With an annular mirror as a WFS pick-off, the focal plane sharpening cannot be performed during closed-loop. Therefore, the shape of the adaptive secondary will be averaged across time during closed-loop, which can then be applied statically while the focal plane sharpening is performed in the science focal plane. This induces an error associated with wavefront variations caused by the source or turbulence within the instrument, that cannot be avoided without changes to the WFS hardware, but can be remedied by repeated measurements in the focal plane. Using the source in the primary focus, this process is performed on-axis for a single instrument configuration. An internal source is then used to measure the field variation, the effect of the k-mirror position, and the different filters by finding the difference with this baseline configuration. This will be done using the single internal diffraction limited source, due to the additional challenges associated with the use of the multimode fibers. As the field variation will then have to be measured sequentially, this process becomes more time consuming, which motivates the choice for the use of an internal source. Allowing a reduction in the amount of technical (day)time on the telescope required.

5. CONCLUSION

Despite the unique architecture of NirvanaVIS, it is still possible to achieve a good correction for non-common path aberrations. By combining the use of a source in the telescope's primary focus with an internal one, using both of the available correctors, and using two different methods to characterize the WFS and science components of the NCPA separately, a strategy was developed that measures the NCPA in all of the instrument's configurations without requiring additional hardware or large amounts of technical (day)time on the telescope. In the coming months this strategy will be tested at the telescope, ahead of the installation and commissioning of the instrument which is expected to commence in 2027.

Figure 5. Difference images for the first 16 Zernike modes (excluding oblique counterparts), shown for both a resolved- and an unresolved PSF. Colorbar units are arbitrary but consistent across the different plots.

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